

COAGULATION OF COLLOIDS AND A TIME CONCENTRATION EQUATION ON THE PRECIPITATION EFFECT OF ELECTROLYTES. PART I

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A simple equation has been found to connect the concentration of precipitating electrolyte and the corresponding time of coagulation of As_2S_3 sol. The equation has the form $C = a + b \cdot 1/t$ where a and b are constants, c , the concentration of electrolyte and t , the time of coagulation.

The constants $a + b$ have been interpreted. 'a' has been explained as the critical concentration to coagulate the sol in infinite time and 'b' has been explained as the excess of concentration over the critical value 'a', which is necessary to coagulate the sol in unit time.

The coagulation of colloids has been extensively studied by numerous authors and various suggestions have been advanced by eminent workers in this field (Smoluchowski, Freundlich, Zsigmondy, Weiser, Kruyt, Dhar, Ghosh, Mukherjee, Joshi and others) to explain the mechanism of rapid and slow coagulations. Freundlich (*Kolloid Z.*, 1918, 23, 163) has shown that velocity of slow coagulation of hydrophobic sols increases very much with the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte, whilst for rapid coagulation it remains constant and is independent of the nature and concentration of the coagulating electrolyte. He has explained the rapid increase in the velocity of slow coagulation by the assumption that the charges on the particles produce a repulsion and only those particles are coagulated the kinetic energy of which is greater than a certain critical value, and that the number of particles having energy greater than the critical value, increases with the concentration of the electrolyte. Kruyt and von Arkel (*Chem. Weekblad*, 1919, 16, 220) measured the concentration effect of electrolytes on the rate of coagulation of the hydrosol of selenium by directly counting the particles and observed the optimum concentration of KCl which had brought about coagulation at a measurable rate. Westgren (*Arkiv Kemi Min. Geol.*, 1918, 7, No. 6) studied the rate of slow coagulation of gold sols by observing colour changes and found it to be dependent on the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte.

Smoluchowski (*Z. Physik*, 1917, 92, 129) has derived on mathematical conception his ingenious equation

$$\Sigma v = \frac{v_0}{1 + t/\tau}$$

which has been worked upon by many authors and has been found to be agreeable with rapid coagulations, but not with slow ones.

The process of coagulation by the charge neutralisation of colloidal particles is so complex that none has been too sure of the exact mechanism of the phenomenon at various stages that follow after the addition of electrolyte to a particular sol. In spite of the extensive amount of work that has been undertaken so far in order to elucidate the phenomenon of coagulation, it is yet interesting to study the relationship between

the time of coagulation and the concentration of electrolyte and to explain the observed result on mathematical ground, if possible.

In this paper we communicate some of our experimental values on the coagulation of As_2S_3 sol by a few electrolytes and their time-concentration effect. The concentration of the electrolyte 'c' and the time of coagulation 't' appear to be connected by a simple equation,

$$c = a + b \cdot 1/t,$$

where 'a' and 'b' are constants. This equation may be regarded as an empirical one for the present.

EXPERIMENTAL

Arsenious sulphide sol was prepared by passing slow bubbles of H_2S into distilled water into which a solution of As_2O_3 was added dropwise slowly. Excess of H_2S was removed from the sol by bubbling pure hydrogen till the sol was free of the smell of H_2S . In the literature we find several methods mentioned by which the coagulation point of a sol has been determined. The most simple method worked upon by various authors is to determine the coagulation point by arranging several test tubes containing the same quantity of sol and keeping its total volume constant by mixing variable quantities of water and electrolyte. The coagulation point is the stage when agglomerated particles just begin to leave the surface. We modified this method by arranging five test tubes containing the same amount of sol (5 c.c.) and the same quantity of electrolyte, the total volume being always 10 c.c. The time of coagulation in each test tube was noted and the average was recorded. The same series was repeated with different amounts of the electrolyte and the time-concentration effect was studied at three different dilutions of the As_2S_3 sol. The observations on the time and concentration are recorded in the following tables and a representative curve, obtained by plotting 'c' against '1/t', is shown.

TABLE I

Coagulation with LiCl.

Amount of As_2S_3 per litre of sol = 1.662 g. (Dilution A).

LiCl added in mM/lit. of sol.	Time of coagula- tion.	1/t.	LiCl added in mM/lit. of sol.	Time of coagula- tion.	1/t.	LiCl added in mM/lit. of sol.	Time of coagula- tion.	1/t.
(c)	(t)		(c)	(t)		(c)	(t)	
Dilution—A.			Dilution— $\frac{1}{2}$ A.			Dilution— $\frac{1}{4}$ A.		
146.3	45	0.0222	250.8	100	0.0100	459.8	50	0.0200
158.8	38	0.0263	292.6	41	0.0244	480.7	20	0.0500
167.2	31.5	0.0317	313.5	31	0.0322	501.6	15	0.0667
188.1	21	0.0476	334.4	18	0.0556	435.4	9	0.1111
209.0	12	0.0833	355.3	9	0.1111			

TABLE II

*Coagulation with NaCl.*Amount of As_2S_3 per litre of sol = 1.662 g. (Dilution A).

c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
Dilution—A.			Dilution— $\frac{1}{2}$ A.			Dilution— $\frac{1}{4}$ A.		
131.5	68	0.0142	144.6	56	0.0178	157.8	42	0.0238
144.6	39	.0257	157.8	36	.0278	170.9	35	.0286
157.8	27	.0370	170.9	27.5	.0364	184.1	27	.0370
170.9	20	.0500	184.1	22.5	.0444	197.2	22	.0455
184.1	17	0.588	210.4	17.5	.0572	210.4	19	.0526

TABLE III

*Coagulation with KCl.*Amount of As_2S_3 per litre of sol = 1.654 g. (Dilution A).

c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
Dilution—A.			Dilution— $\frac{1}{2}$ A.			Dilution— $\frac{1}{4}$ A.		
133.8	45	0.0222	163.5	35	0.0208	208.1	33	0.0303
148.7	27	.0370	178.4	25	.0400	223.0	26.5	.0377
163.3	23	.0435	193.2	20.5	.0488	230.4	18.5	.0540
178.4	15	.0667	208.5	15	.0667	237.9	15.5	.0645
193.2	11	.0909	223.0	13.5	.0741	252.7	11	.0909

TABLE IV

*Coagulation with RbCl (Fig. 1).*Amount of As_2S_3 per litre of sol = 1.662 g. (Dilution A).

c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
Dilution—A.			Dilution— $\frac{1}{2}$ A.			Dilution— $\frac{1}{4}$ A.		
92.4	80	0.0125	110.9	56	0.0177	129.4	38	0.0259
106.3	33	.0303	120.1	35.5	.0282	138.6	29	.0345
116.9	27	.0370	129.4	25.5	.0393	147.8	23	.0434
120.1	21	.0476	138.6	20	.0500	157.1	18	.0556
129.4	17.5	.0572	147.8	18	.0556	166.4	15	.0667

TABLE V
Coagulation with CsNO_3 .

Amount of As_2S_3 per litre of sol = 1.921 g. (Dilution A).

c.	Dilution-A.		Dilution- $\frac{1}{2}$ A.			Dilution- $\frac{1}{4}$ A.		
	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
53.4	54	0.0185	64.1	55	0.0182	85.4	75	0.0133
58.7	34	.0294	69.4	33	.0303	90.8	45	.0222
64.1	24.5	.0408	74.8	20.5	.0488	96.1	32	.0313
74.8	18	.0556	85.4	11	.0909	101.5	26	.0385
89.1	11.5	.0870	106.8	3	.3333			

TABLE VI

Coagulation with BaCl_2 .

Amount of As_2S_3 per litre of sol = 1.921 g. (Dilution A).

c.	Dilution-A.		Dilution- $\frac{1}{2}$ A.			Dilution- $\frac{1}{4}$ A.		
	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
1.028	45	0.0222	1.234	26	0.0385	1.336	23	0.0435
1.131	36	.0278	1.336	17	.0588	1.439	21.5	.0465
1.234	26	.0477	1.439	15	.0667	1.542	18	.0556
1.285	16.8	.0596	1.542	11.5	.0870	1.646	14.5	.0690
1.336	13	.0769				1.747	13	.0770
1.131	42.5	.0235						

TABLE VII

Coagulation with AlCl_3 .

Amount of As_2S_3 per litre of sol = 1.671 g. (Dilution A).

c.	Dilution-A.		Dilution- $\frac{1}{2}$ A.			Dilution- $\frac{1}{4}$ A.		
	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
0.40	60	0.0167	0.40	36	0.0278	0.32	25	0.0400
.44	40	.0250	.42	30	.0333	.36	17	.0588
.46	26	.0462	.44	25	.0400	.40	12	.0833
.48	18	.0556	.46	19	.0526	.44	8.5	.1176
.52	12	.0833	.48	15	.0667			

DISCUSSION

The above experiments lead to the following conclusions:

(i) Time-concentration behaviour is normal in the sense that time of coagulation is reduced by increase in the concentration of electrolyte, a phenomenon which has also been observed before.

(ii) When concentration and reciprocal of the time of coagulation are plotted (Fig. 1) straight lines are obtained with all electrolytes irrespective of their nature

FIG. 1

Coagulation with RbCl

and concentration of the sol. Hence 'c' and 't' can be connected by the equation $c = a + b \cdot 1/t$, 'a' and 'b' being constants. Table VII gives the values of 'a' and 'b' as obtained graphically.

TABLE VIII

Electrolyte.	Value of 'a' in millimoles			Value of 'b' in mM/minute.		
	Dil. A.	Dil. 5/3A	Dil. 5/2A.	Dil. A.	Dil. 5/3A.	Dil. 5/2A.
LiCl	135	255	443	1000	1250	1000
NaCl	108.5	112.5	120	1350	1660	1700
KCl	110	139	176	1030	1075	1000
RbCl	80	96.5	109.5	860	830	860
CsNO ₃	49	60	77.5	320	290	610
BaCl ₂	1.03	0.95	0.965	4.06	7.20	10.00
AlCl ₃	0.365	0.359	0.246	2.2	1.88	1.85

Now the main interest centres round the interpretation of the two constants 'a' and 'b', which it is not possible to do completely at the present stage of our experiments. The obvious interpretation of 'a', as seen in the graph, is the value of 'c' at $1/t=0$, i.e. at $t=\infty$, and hence 'a' is the maximum amount of electrolyte which can be added to the sol without effecting any coagulation. In other words, we may call it the critical stability concentration of the electrolyte for the particular sol. On what factors does this critical stability concentration depend will be elucidated by further elaboration of experiments.

The physical interpretation of 'b' is not so explicit as that of 'a'. It can, however, be interpreted by putting $t=1$, when $(c-a)$ becomes equal to b . This means that 'b' is that concentration of the electrolyte which should be added to the sol, in excess of the critical stability concentration, in order to precipitate it in unit time.

(iii) The dilution of sol does not seem to produce any such abnormal change in the sol particles as to deform the characteristic shape of the curve. In case of many electrolytes the straight lines at different dilutions are parallel to each other, showing *a priori* that on dilution the number of particles in a given volume decreases in the same ratio in which the distance between them increases, so that the amount of electrolyte, in excess of the critical value, in order to precipitate it in unit time remains the same. Thus 'b' remains constant and the parallelism between the lines can thus be explained. There are, however, such cases of dilution effect where the lines are not parallel. This can be ascribed to the change in the size or charge or both of the colloidal particles when the sol is diluted. In this connection it is necessary to observe that the experiments at various dilutions should be carried on almost simultaneously, which it has not been possible to do in certain cases. The values of 'b' should be very susceptible to the age of the sol and that has been actually observed with LiCl and NaCl at dilutions A and $5/3A$, with BaCl₂ and CsNO₃ at the dilution $5/2A$. In these cases the time gap between the experimental observations at different dilutions was longer than in others.

(iv) The value of 'a', which we term critical stability concentration, shows a normal variation with the valency of the precipitating ion (Table VIII) in that it decreases as the valency of the precipitating ion increases. It is interesting, further, to observe that generally higher the weight of the precipitating ion, the lower the value of 'a' even for ions of the same valency.

(v) Table VIII brings out another interesting fact in the values of 'b'. As the valency of the coagulating ion increases, the value of 'b' decreases. This observation fits in with our interpretation of 'b'. Since the coagulating power of ions increases with valency, the value of the amount necessary to coagulate the sol in unit time should decrease and 'b', which is the excess of this value over critical concentration, should naturally get smaller and smaller.

(vi) The variation in the precipitating power of an electrolyte with the dilution of a sol shows that in the case of monovalent electrolytes and also with BaCl₂, the dilution effect is abnormal but it is normal with AlCl₃. The abnormality for monovalent ions is more marked in the case of lighter ions than the heavier ones. Previous author (Weiser, Mukerjee, Dhar, Ghosh and others) have also observed this abnormality and have offered various suggestions to explain it. More and varied experiments are being planned to explain this abnormality on fundamental concepts of coagulation phenomenon.

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